

Exploring Antimicrobial Efficacy of Ashoka Tree Extracts against *E. coli*: A Comparative Study Using Polar and Non-Polar Solvents

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Abstract:

In this study, we used both polar and non-polar solvents to investigate the antibacterial properties of Ashoka tree extracts against *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) bacteria. Our research seeks to confirm the medicinal potential of the Ashoka tree (*Saraca asoca*), which has long been revered in traditional medicine for its capacity to heal bacterial infections. Using an analogous process, we extracted bioactive compounds from the bark and leaves of Ashoka trees using polar (water and ethanol) and non-polar (hexane and chloroform) solvents. Our observations reveal that the antibacterial activity of the polar and non-polar extracts vary significantly, emphasising the importance of solvent selection in the extraction of bioactive components. We also assessed each extract's minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) to determine its efficacy against *E. coli*. We also conducted phytochemical analysis to evaluate the presence of secondary metabolites responsible for the observed antibacterial effect. Our findings give significant new information for future studies targeted at developing novel antimicrobial medications by emphasising the potential of Ashoka tree extracts as natural replacements for synthetic antibiotics.

Introduction

Medicinal herbs have been shown to be an effective treatment for a variety of human illnesses. The need for longevity and relief from pain and discomfort pushed early man to explore his near natural environment, utilising plants, animal products, and minerals, among other things. Medicinal plants include a variety of natural compounds with varied degrees of bioactivity.

^[1]Traditional medicine and herbal medications are gaining popularity again these days. Because green medications are seen as safer as and more reliable than manufactured treatments. Many synthetic medications cause negative side effects. ^[2]

An herb is a tiny herbaceous plant and its parts (stem, leaves, flowers, seeds, fruits, bark, roots, rhizomes, and wood) that are valued for their medicinal, fragrant, or savoury properties. Medicinal plants produce and contain a wide range of chemical components that act on the body and are utilised as medications, agrochemicals, flavours^[3] & fragrances, ingredients, food

additives, and insecticides. Nowadays, many regularly used medications are of herbal origin. Indeed, around 25% of all prescribed medications contain at least one active ingredient derived from plant material.^[4] Medicinal plants have the ability to boost the economy and create jobs for unemployed young people. The harvesting and processing of medicinal herbs is believed to employ at least 35 million people in India each year. Medicinal plant culture may serve as a successful model for their development.^[5,6]

Therapeutic plants and herbs have contributed significantly to the development of many therapeutic systems such as Ayurveda, Siddha, and Unani. Medicinal plants have long been known to benefit humanity.^[7] Medicinal plants are seen as a potential link between long-term economic growth, cheap health care, and biodiversity conservation. As a result, there is an urgent need to develop policies and strategies to maximise the potential of medicinal plants for multifaceted socioeconomic development.^[8]

Material and Methods:

PREPARATION OF THE EXTRACTS

The Ashoka Tree Samples were properly cleansed with double-distilled water. The Ashoka tree samples were chopped into small slices and dried at 350 degrees Celsius for 2-6 hours. The dry ingredients were then finely ground into powder using a mixer grinder. The powder was stored at -200 degrees Celsius in airtight plastic bags.^[9]

The Soxhlet apparatus was built to extract Ashoka Tree Samples (*Polyalthia longifolia*) [plant leaf, flower, seed, seed coat, stem, and bark of plant] with various polar and non-polar solvents such as methanol, ethanol, chloroform, and n-hexane.^[10] 20g Ashoka tree samples were extracted using the Soxhlet method with 200 ml of polar and non-polar solvents. All extracts were evaporated until a powder extract sample was produced and kept at 40°C for subsequent analysis.^[11]

MICROORGANISMS

The bacterial and fungal cultures were obtained from the Microbial Type Culture Collection (MTCC), Institute of Microbial Technology, Chandigarh and National Collection of Industrial Microorganism (NCIM) Pune, India.^[12] Bacterial cultures, *Escherichia coli* (NCIM-2065), *Bacillus subtilis* (NCIM-2196), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (NCIM-5029) were used for the antimicrobial studies.

Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration and Minimum antimicrobial activity

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) is the lowest concentration of a substance, medicine, or natural plant extract that prevents the growth of bacteria, viruses, and fungi.^[13] The MIC against Ashoka Tree Samples was calculated by creating high-concentration solutions of medicines, natural compounds, or isolated bioactive compounds in vitro, incubating the solutions with various batches of cultured bacteria or fungi, and quantifying the findings using broth micro dilution.^[14] While MIC is the lowest dosage of an antimicrobial agent used to impede apparent growth, it is also the lowest concentration of antimicrobial agents that kill bacteria and fungi. The most often used media are nutritional broth and Sabouraud's dextrose broth, which are known for their ability to sustain microbial growth and lack of inhibitors to popular antibiotics.^[15] The concentration of antimicrobial agents is adjusted to the proper level by combining stock antimicrobial agents with medium. To obtain a gradient, the adjusted antimicrobial agent (fruit waste extract) is serially diluted in a 96-well plate.

Result:

Determination of MIC (Minimum Inhibitory Concentration)

Methanol extract <i>E.coli</i>						
	50 µg/ml	100 µg/ml	150 µg/ml	200 µg/ml	P Value	F value
PLANT LEAF	0.42±0.05	0.24±0.07	0.30±0.06	0.28±0.07	0.0378	3.861
FLOWER	0.28±0.08	0.15±0.04	0.44±0.00	0.52±0.02	0.0001	115
SEED	0.56±0.10	0.24±0.02	0.59±0.10	0.37±0.10	0.0005	13.74
SEED COAT	0.54±0.03	0.73±0.10	0.54±0.10	0.14±0.04	0.0001	24.60
STEM	0.63±0.12	0.32±0.13	0.49±0.16	0.59±0.10	0.0033	8.260
BARK OF PLANT	0.68±0.08	0.28±0.09	0.34±0.16	0.45±0.20	0.0014	10.41
Positive Control (Gentamicin) 50 µg/ml	0.25±0.01					
Negative Control (<i>E.coli</i>) 50 µg/ml	0.87±0.00					

Table:1 Minimum inhibitory activity of methanolic extract against *E.coli*

Figure:1 Minimum inhibitory activity of methanolic extract against *E.coli*

Ethanol extract <i>E.coli</i>						
	50 µg/ml	100 µg/ml	150 µg/ml	200 µg/ml	P Value	F Value
PLANT LEAF	0.53±0.05	0.36±0.02	0.29±0.03	0.32±0.08	0.0001	71.48
FLOWER	0.34±0.09	0.17±0.02	0.19±0.04	0.36±0.05	0.0001	80.70
SEED	0.62±0.13	0.61±0.02	0.75±0.10	0.61±0.10	0.0204	4.786
SEED COAT	0.71±0.11	0.53±0.04	0.44±0.12	0.11±0.03	0.0024	9.481
STEM	0.46±0.12	0.69±0.13	0.24±0.06	0.51±0.07	0.0001	19.04
BARK OF PLANT	0.67±0.06	0.61±0.06	0.19±0.08	0.39±0.24	0.0004	13.85
Positive Control (Gentamicin) 50 µg/ml	0.25±0.01					
Negative Control (<i>E.coli</i>) 50 µg/ml	0.87±0.00					

Table: 2 Minimum inhibitory activity of ethanolic extract against *E.coli*

Figure: 2 - Minimum inhibitory activity of ethanolic extract against *E.coli*

Chloroform extract <i>E.coli</i>						
	50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	150 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	P Value	F Value
PLANT LEAF	0.72 $\pm$ 0.21	0.52 $\pm$ 0.11	0.71 $\pm$ 0.06	0.31 $\pm$ 0.02	0.0005	13.45
FLOWER	0.54 $\pm$ 0.02	0.54 $\pm$ 0.01	0.40 $\pm$ 0.12	0.32 $\pm$ 0.02	0.0001	39.88
SEED	0.63 $\pm$ 0.03	0.43 $\pm$ 0.03	0.46 $\pm$ 0.06	0.37 $\pm$ 0.05	0.0001	68.37
SEED COAT	0.63 $\pm$ 0.05	0.66 $\pm$ 0.08	0.87 $\pm$ 0.30	0.23 $\pm$ 0.06	0.0019	9.533
STEM	0.68 $\pm$ 0.25	0.56 $\pm$ 0.10	0.45 $\pm$ 0.17	0.37 $\pm$ 0.13	0.0219	4.672
BARK OF PLANT	0.78 $\pm$ 0.09	0.85 $\pm$ 0.04	0.44 $\pm$ 0.20	0.47 $\pm$ 0.13	0.0020	9.407
Positive Control (Gentamicin) 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.25 $\pm$ 0.01					
Negative Control (<i>E.coli</i>) 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.87 $\pm$ 0.00					

Table: 3 Minimum inhibitory activity of chloroform extract against *E.coli***Figure: 3** Minimum inhibitory activity of chloroform extract against *E.coli*

n-Hexane extract <i>E.coli</i>						
	50 µg/ml	100 µg/ml	150 µg/ml	200 µg/ml	P Value	F Value
PLANT LEAF	0.84±0.10	0.45±0.03	0.28±0.09	0.27±0.01	0.0001	57.23
FLOWER	0.73±0.09	0.42±0.09	0.40±0.03	0.36±0.03	0.0001	36.51
SEED	0.68±0.04	0.43±0.02	0.56±0.04	0.40±0.17	0.0003	15.63
SEED COAT	0.45±0.04	0.61±0.06	0.18±0.06	0.06±0.01	0.0001	165.2
STEM	0.65±0.02	0.48±0.04	0.68±0.08	0.34±0.05	0.0001	45.82
BARK OF PLANT	0.61±0.07	0.46±0.03	0.46±0.04	0.32±0.02	0.0001	78.81
Positive Control (Gentamicin) 50 µg/ml	0.25±0.01					
Negative Control (<i>E.coli</i>) 50 µg/ml	0.87±0.00					

Table:4 Minimum inhibitory activity of hexane extract against *E.coli*

Figure: 4 Minimum inhibitory activity of hexane extract against *E.coli*

The effects of the extracts on *E. coli* in chloroform, n-hexane, methanol, and ethanol all demonstrate significant antibacterial activity against various plant components.

All measured amounts of *E. coli* were consistently stopped from growing by methanol, ethanol, and chloroform extract. This means that these extracts contain substantial antibacterial properties. Certain extracts exhibit greater activity at specific dosages, as evidenced by the significant inhibition observed at higher concentrations, indicating a dose-dependent response.

However, the n-hexane extract had significant antibacterial action at all doses, implying that it contains potent antibacterial components as well. In contrast to the other extracts, the maximal inhibition was observed at lower dosages, indicating a separate mechanism of action.

Overall, our findings highlight the potential of plant extracts as an antibacterial agent source. Additional research into the specific compounds producing the reported activity, as well as their modes of action, could give valuable information for the development of new antimicrobial medications.

Conclusion:

Finally, our findings demonstrate the therapeutic properties of Ashoka tree extracts against bacterial infections, particularly those induced by *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*). We found significant differences in antibacterial activity between polar and non-polar solvents when extracting bioactive compounds, emphasising the importance of solvent selection. The assessment of the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) further verified the extracts' efficacy against *E. coli*. Furthermore, the results of our Phytochemical research confirmed the presence of secondary metabolites responsible for the observed antibacterial action. These findings emphasise the potential of Ashoka tree extracts as natural replacements for synthetic antibiotics and give critical new information for future research projects aimed at developing revolutionary antimicrobial medicines.

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